

Report on cognitive experience with VR

Project: Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT

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PROJECT SUMMARY

This project aims to connect the existing strengths, identify and overcome weaknesses and plan for future competitiveness in the fields of policy, practice and experience. More concretely, the project's objectives are, on the one hand, to explore the long-standing strengths and pervasive gaps in European competitiveness and policies for competitiveness. This includes ways of 'measuring' 'analysing' and 'evaluating' the impact of policies and strategic pathways. On the other hand, the project aspires to place attention to the active preparation for the future in the area of audiences by exploring audience preferences and their generation, as well as modes of film content production. The latter are elements which today's youth will carry and engage with in the coming decades as makers and consumers, as well as industry and policy leaders. Therefore, the consortium interrogates not only the 'what is' but also the 'what has been' and 'what will be' with fresh lenses. REBOOT's ambition is to provide a full set of knowledge of the European film industry, which maximises its existing strengths, combined with strategic and tactical dimensions of action for the optimisation of the potential held in European youth publics, understood both as emerging audiences and as citizens. Specifically, the ambition of the project combines several dimensions, which reinforce each other but are listed separately for analytical purposes (and in no particular order): a) increasing support for young people's engagement with European film; b) strengthening the place of the EU in the global audiovisual economy, particularly in light of the rise of video on demand (VOD); c) supporting cultural diversity in the EU film industry; d) addressing the need for a different understanding of competitiveness and relevant indicators in this context; and e) recognising and supporting the importance for the EU of film and, more broadly, of the cultural and creative sector as a geopolitical asset.

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1. DELIVERABLE ABSTRACTS

As part of the WP5.3.1 “Study of the cognitive abilities of young content creators in Mixed Reality,” the role of UCA research team is to delve and explore the intricate relationships between cinema and emerging immersive communication technologies.

These latter are unfolding along diverse vectors of industrial and commercial progression, encompassing, the realm of video games, remote learning, metaverse communication, urban scenography, and intelligent signage. Ultimately, the aforementioned developments are culminating in the media of individual and collective mobility.

This study interrogates the propensity to bring together cinema and immersive technologies through the creation of narrative and aesthetic artefacts, facilitated by 360° recording equipment and projected within the Virtual Reality headset, one of three distinct environments for immersive spectatorship, alongside the 270°/3D video wall and the 360°/180° dome.

Following an extensive overview of various cultural policy strategies across the world, a prospective European strategy is envisioned focusing on the convergence of cinema and immersive technologies, commonly referred to as Mixed Reality.

In order to go beyond the ephemeral nature of contemporary societal opinions and trends, often susceptible to commercial influences and fleeting fashions, an experimental methodology of 'informational load analysis' was opted for, to assess the cognitive processes underlying spectatorship, thereby accounting for the success or failure of innovations in the realm of creative media.

The investigation commences with a theoretical reflection and a comprehensive review of the historical relationships between cinema and techniques in general.

Subsequently, the following sections present a reflection on the experimental protocol and its conditions of application, leading to the description of a series of cognitive tests that compare the viewing of immersive narrative productions in the Virtual Reality headset, with reference to the natural perception of the same scenes. This approach is based upon the seminal work of Shimamura, a prominent researcher and precursor in the field of kinematic cognition, who has developed methods to mitigate experimental artifacts generated by different media languages, including film language.

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The fundamental hypothesis underlying this approach is to consider that the main leverage of the evolution of social cognition is not marketing or current trend, nor even familiarisation with the more or less democratised equipment. Rather, it is the effective creativity in the field that interests us. The empirical evidence from our experimental results unequivocally supports this hypothesis, revealing a significant disparity in cognitive abilities between creative and non-creative students.

In other words, if Europe leverages its incentive system to converge cinema and Mixed Reality techniques, as exemplified by the prominent European film festivals, namely the "Mostra - Immersive section" and "Cannes - Immersive Competition", it would be prudent to complement direct support for creative projects with investments in education and training programs focused on Mixed and Immersive Reality, spanning from secondary education to master's level. In the wake of the limited adoption of Virtual Reality technology, an education-centric approach appears to be the most promising strategy for fostering growth in our area of interest.

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2. DELIVERABLE CONTEXT

2.1 Preliminary considerations

The REBOOT programme must undertake a comprehensive audit of the current situation and dynamics of European cinema. Deliberately oriented towards the future, its primary objective is, among other things, to provide compelling arguments and evidence-based insights to inform the decisions of future experts responsible for distributing European funding for cinematographic creation. It aims to offer convincing elements regarding the progression of cinema-related activities sector, spanning the entire value chain, encompassing elements from conception, through production and distribution, culminating in audience engagement and the fostering of a new cinematographic culture in the broad sense. These imperatives stem from the foundational documents underpinning the origin of this project.

The European authorities assume a role as instigators, with the potential to exert influence over the creative sector of reference, through the implementation incentive measures appearing under the common denominator of proactive strategies.

Our consortium comprises 12 research teams, each bringing their unique expertise to the task of diagnosing present events and future trajectories of European cinema within the context of rival industries. Developing a fair vision of European cinematography implies to adopt a multifaceted approach that transcends mere comparative analysis with other industries. Instead, our research will delve into the complexities' intercultural exchanges, both on the Old Continent and on a global scale, to identify emerging trends and patterns that are reshaping the cinematographic landscape.

Our horizon then opens onto the ecosystem of European cinematography grappling with its competitors and against a backdrop of currents running through globalised culture. It is the latter which will provide plausible observation criteria for our study.

Since the late 90s, it has widely been acknowledged that the most significant and profound shaking in world culture comes from the digitalisation of creative practices and communication fields. Therefore, one of the most important things to investigate within REBOOT programme will be the interplay between cinema and the digital technology sector.

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2.2. Cinema and technology

Since its inception, cinema has maintained privileged links with the emerging industries of the 19th century. Enabled by advancements in chemistry, optics and mechanics, cinema took advantage over the 60-year-old medium that was photography, positioning itself as a creative response to the industrialisation of individual and collective mobility of societies during the colonial era. Additionally, cinema has been united with parallel development in life and human sciences, including physiology, ethology and psychology.

Technological development therefore emerges as the primordial vector of the dynamics of cinema. Its stages mark out the successive phases of development, of the narrative techniques of the film medium and of the socio-technical devices associated with it: industry, cultural policy, art critique, the consecration instances, training, education and spectator association movements.

Direct and binocular animation, the reversible camera with collective projection by backlight, different films and different speeds of their scrolling, the adaptation of the architecture of the viewing places, the sonification, the different capture and projection formats, the transition from 2D to 3D, aerial imagery, multisensory experiences, immersive capture and display combined with the digitisation of all classic techniques with the emergence of new auxiliary digital techniques such as motion capture and artificial imaging, all these inventions and improvements punctuate the history of cinema as a major cultural phenomenon of our civilisation.

2.3. Unravelling the paradox of the technological status in cinema

With the perspective of time, it is appropriate to note the existence of a singular moment in the history of the 125-year-old film industry.

Cinema theorists (Bordwell, D., & Thompson, K., 2002) do note a strong and symmetrical relationship between technological innovations and narrative techniques of the genre, but only over the period from the origins until the 1970s. We note that the panoply of means of filmic language remains relatively stable since this last period which not without reason can be considered as a sort of **apogee of the film**. And if today's creators have nothing to envy of the celebrities from the 70s, the fact remains that, in the opinion of experts, the revolution comparable to the transition between mute cinema and sound cinema has not happened. during the last half century. The improvement in the quality of the image, the scale of the decor or the perfection of special effects accompany the narrative patterns which remain relatively immutable.

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Should we compare this stabilization with the stagnation of the narrative techniques of the literary novel from the same period? Some specialists insist on the fact that despite the increase in editorial possibilities linked to new distribution techniques in digital networks, the only new literary trends to appear in the 21st century, autofiction, magical realism, or positive minimalism are in fact only “network” adaptations of narrative techniques already known in the 1970s. The question of similarities between the filmic and literary sectors remains unresolved but it does not concern us here.

In accordance with the intentions of the REBOOT project, we pose questions about the future evolution of the dynamics of cinema.

Will world cinema, and particularly European cinema, find sufficient creative resources to go beyond stagnant narrative genres and will it thus rise to the contemporary challenges that stand before us in the 20s of the 21st century?

Why do we ask this question today when by looking at cinematographic culture publications, such as “Les Cahiers du Cinéma” in France, “Sight & Sound” in the United Kingdom or even “Filmkritik” in Germany, we note the abundance of current topics, which borders on exhaustivity, and which confirms the central position of this media in the European, even global, cultural offering?

This appears to be a paradox: contemporary cinema speaks to us well about the challenges of our world and at the same time this “duty of topics” is rendered, it's the case to say it, in a cinematographic language with a topology which falls below expectations for resolving the complexity and the scale specific to the phenomena of our time.

This aporia stands at the place of questioning that we hope is the most fertile for our research within the framework of the REBOOT program.

2.4. The paradoxical status of technological innovation in contemporary cinema – the different existing strategies

Another difficulty comes from the very status of the technological innovations which interfere with current cinema. If, for example, research on optical sound between 1911 and 1927 (Eugene Lauste, Lee De Forest) directly served the film industry, culminating in the Fox Film Corporation patent, the same cannot be said of recent advances coming from fundamental research and industrial applications in Information Technology.

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Here, cinematography, unlike the communications sector, does not play the role of main backer. In particular, the origins of Virtual Reality, involved today in a vast sector of so-called Mixed Reality technologies, first came from military concerns, in the 60s and 70s, to flow during the 90s into civilian applications such as spatialisation and data visualisation (Sobieszczanski, M., 2019), while the most recent patents are most often registered by the gaming, merchandising, guidance of mobility and roaming communication industries, etc.

If some observers (Bergeron, P., 1982) note the existence of related points between cinematography and the industries consuming innovation in the digital sector, especially in terms of thematic inspiration (Bersini, H., 2009), the confirmed facts of technological transfer force us to adopt a more cautious attitude. Indeed, instead of massive transfers, it is rather a timid porosity between the two parallel domains, that we record.

But once again paradoxically, we see that the slightest technological transfer in this field leads to major resonances in cinematographic culture, which is not surprising since these facts are remarkable and noticed. It is therefore not shocking that different cinematography are positioning themselves in the face of these innovations and making them their vector of progress, supported by adapted cultural incentive policies and industrial achievements attested by patents, standards and formats.

This is how South Korean cinematography developed the ScreenX format, distributed viewing equipment in multiplexes in Asia, the USA and Europe and offered facilities to young creators wishing to undertake experiments within the framework of multi-screen and immersive cinema (3 screens at 270°). China promotes another strategy: the state provides aid to creators who work on the hybridisation of cinema and video games, with the assortment of narrative techniques specific to the latter: the intervention of the spectator in the unfolding action, alternative screenwriting, multiplayer experiences, etc. The North American industry is banking on 3D in the IMAX and IMAX DOME standards. Productions adapted to this environment have fluctuated since the peak in 2008, focusing on very lucrative blockbusters, without however developing a broad 3D culture in terms of training creators and educating spectators.

Europe at the level of common central bodies remains quite passive and delegates the issue to national industries. Here we see the necessity for a **statistical and systemic study** to contextualize certain well-known facts, such as for example the strategy of significant aid that certain Baltic countries allocate to the hybridisation of cinema and Virtual Reality, or the

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dropper-drip style help provided to digital creation in France by Centre National du Cinéma et de l'Image Animée.

2.5. The research methodology on the founding paradoxes of cinema

To address the double paradox of cinematographic culture we have several possibilities, in particular the one which is most obvious: the conduct of a simultaneous and symmetrical study of the complexity of the problems treated and the topologies of their expression, in the sense of the treatment of space by the geometry inherent in the means of capture/viewing. This study was made for some masterpieces of the 70s, and more especially for the two most emblematic scenes, the finale in "[Professione : reporter](#)" by Michelangelo Antonioni and the torture scene in "Salò o le 120 giornate di Sodoma" by Pier Paolo Pasolini (Sobieszczanski, M., 2010). If the results of the analyses show that the giants of cinema of the classical age clearly announce their desire to escape from the restraints imposed on them by the geometry of the space of the filmic system, in which they are precursors of the new era, as much the folding of space on itself in "Inception" by Christopher Nolan admits the lack of this new geometry, 40 years later...

But, despite this suggestive theoretical result, the method suffers from its speculative nature and its inaccuracy.

Can we undertake a more exact and more formal study, based on considering the follow doublet: the narrated reality and the topology of the means of capture/viewing? To answer this, we must define what the correlation is based on, on the one hand the themes covered and the difficulty thinking their complexity or the status of the facts themselves, of knowledge and interpretations of reality, and on the other hand the narrative structures of different forms of expression: codified gesture, oral storytelling, pictorial and musical techniques, writing, photography, or cinema. In other words: on what set of parameters/variables of the apprehended creatively reality is indexed, as mathematicians would say, the characteristics of narrative techniques and especially those of the art of movement that is cinema?

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2.6. Spectatorial cognition – the third term of an experimental study

The difficulty of the challenge is immense, requiring a vast and multi-year investigation, poorly adapted to the scientific standards practiced in furtive fields such as cinema.

The solution would, however, come from a third term. We notice that spectatorial cognition is the place of focus of both shared causalities: the spectator thinks of reality with the creator, and it is towards him, in the gesture of the invention of new cognitive ergonomics, that the narrative means are oriented. Spectatorial cognition constitutes for us the best experimental environment in which the contents and their filmic format constitute efficient and configurable inputs. In this we intend to reconnect with vast studies in kinematic cognition developed since the seminal work of the school of Arthur P. Shimamura (Shimamura, A. P., 2013).

2.7. The experimental method applied to spectatorial cognition

1. Parameterisation by extraction and memorisation of information

Among the characteristics of spectatorial cognition we retain the most basic, those relating to the extraction and memorization of information during the spectatorship of narrated/mediated reality.

2. Parameterisation through the semantisation of environments

From the extraction and memorisation of information, the spectator engages in higher-level processing which makes it possible to construct the complex semantics of the scene of reality represented to carry out intellectual actions such as spatial and temporal orientation or causal deduction and anticipation.

3. Parameterisation by emotional states

As a result of semantic processing the spectator is subject to different emotional states which in turn engages him in spectatorship with renewed potential.

4. The experimental framework – the choice of technological environments

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Among the digital technologies interfering with the cinema sector, we believe that so-called **immersive technologies** present the greatest potential for hybridisation. This trend is particularly observed in imaging in the broad sense and in the field of sound and music.

Our choice falls on three environments, **the Virtual Reality headsets, the 180° immersive dome and the 270° autostereoscopic 3D video wall**. This latest device uses the South Korean ScreenX format and adds autostereoscopic 3D from the New York company QOOBEX. It's a prototype.

5. The expectations of the experimental study – the working hypotheses

Thanks to the application of the experimental protocol to different control groups of the populations to be studied, we intend to obtain results that can guide future arbiters of European cultural policies in the matter of hybridization between cinema and digital technologies, and especially immersive technologies.

3. HYPOTHESIS

1. The first Hypothesis

The study must confirm the hypothesis of the advantages of investment in supporting technologically hybrid creation.

2. The subsidiary hypothesis

The cinema/MR hybridisation will have its impact on the future of cinema but at the same time it will contribute to the transfer of narrative technics and the industrial prototyping that results from them to environmental media such as collective and individual media of mobility. This will create new economic opportunities for both cinema and the media sector as a whole.

3. The second hypothesis

The hybridization of cinema and so-called immersive digital technologies responds to the necessity for the evolution of social cognition, particularly in the field of spatial representation and assistance by technological means with spatial orientation.

4. The subsidiary hypothesis

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Today's spectator needs the motor initiative in his reception of information about reality through visual and sound mediation.

5. The third hypothesis

The key to the success of hybridisation is to be found in the training of creators and the education of the public.

6. The subsidiary hypothesis

The manipulation of environmental/immersive image and spatialized sound leads to the emergence of the special cognitive skills and in turn creates a need for immersion in the mediation of visual and sound information.

4. THE CHOICE OF GROUPS

The weighting of results in relation to the characteristics of control groups is the basis of any experimental study. In accordance with the working hypotheses, we will alternate classic groups according to the criteria of age and socio-professional involvement but the greatest expectations involving the third hypothesis, relating to creative training and education, we will put the emphasis on the contrastive study of groups initiated and uninitiated to creative practices in immersive media. The public of two years of the ICCD/CREATES/UCA M1 and M2 master's course will be concerned here.

5. ELEMENTS FOR THE EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOL

The following elements are the basis for the development of the experimental protocol aimed at measuring the cognitive impact of 360°/270°/3D film creations.

6. VARIATIONAL METHOD: THE VISUAL PARAMETERS OF THE “SCENE-SPHERE/SPECTATOR” SYSTEM

1. Variation of scene-sphere side parameters

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Scene-sphere brightness

Dynamics of the elements filling the scene-sphere

2. Topology/arrangement of visible elements of the scene-sphere

Concentric distance: 3.6m, 10m, 20m

Angular layout

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Visual overlay

Density/complexity of visual elements

3. Variation of spectator side parameters

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Semantic variations of landscape types: interior, urban landscape, rural landscape, natural landscape, etc.

4. Variations in the emotional ambiances of the scene-sphere

5. Categorisation of the viewer's visual field

Orientation of the prime-frontality (the portion of the sphere delimited by the physiological visual field without moving eyes and head)

6. Vision motor categories

Frontal vision: prime frontality with eye movement

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Peripheral vision: the need of head movement

7. Management/monitoring of attention points

(“In the Blink of a Mind Attention” - Jessica Brillhart, The Language of VR)

8. Ocular exploration of prime frontality

Ocular exploration with eye motor skills

Exploration with head movement

Exploration with body movement

Quantitative categories of vision

Holistic vision

Detailed view

Interactional categories of vision

Vision of physical interactions

Vision of corporal interactions

Vision of psychic interactions

9. Permutation of narrative sequences

Antecedence

Posteriority

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10. Spectator tasks

Search for hidden objects

Remembering details

Construction of scene-sphere semantics

Orientation and spatial memory – outlines of the spatial situation of the scene-sphere

Anticipation of the posterior sequence

Deduction of the previous session

Emergence of emotional states

11. Experimental methodologies of information load and its management

Oculometry - measures (OM) (eye tracking)

Detail Count Measures

Measures of memorization of narrative sequences

Spatial orientation measurements by freehand drawing

Measurements of skin conductance (electrodermal activity)

12. Population sample categories

A1 - creative group of novices before the first creative experiments

A2 - creative group of novices after the first creative experiences – master students

B1 - non-creative group, 18-30 years old

B2 - non-creative group, 30 years and over

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7. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOL

Natural perception VS 'spherical scene' perception

Description of the experimental protocol: experiments on April 17th and May 16th, 2024.

Wednesday April 17th, 2024: Participants

Semantisation of the environment, situational logic, anticipation and causality.

A sample of 10 students enrolled in the first year of the ICCD and DISTIC courses of the master's degree in Information-Communication at Université Côte d'Azur was selected for this study. This sample included 7 women and 3 men, with 8 of whom were aged between 18 and 25 and 2 between 26 and 35. The students were divided into two groups of 5, one comprising 5 ICCD students (the 'creative' group) and the other 5 DISTIC students (the 'non-creative' group), who had voluntarily taken part in the 'natural perception' experiment. Participation was voluntary, and no compensation, either in the form of ECTS credits or remuneration was provided.

1. Protocol group

The organisation of the experiment was carried out jointly by M. Sobieszczanski and myself (Léa Gibilaro). Together, we coordinated the planning of the meeting by communicating the agenda to the participants. In addition, because of her involvement in post-production, Anissa Fahmi was unable to volunteer for the experiments, so she was included in the protocol group. Thus, the data collection benefited from the presence of two facilitators: Anissa Fahmi was in charge of the video recording of the participants' reactions, while I was responsible for organising the experiment, clarifying the objectives of the session to the participants, and ensuring that they were achieved. Carole Marconi, who worked on the project, was responsible for setting up the set and supervising the two actors and their costumes.

2. Stimuli

The two actors performed the theatrical scene in front of the audience in two adjacent rooms, creating, as I had envisaged in the script, a physical separation corresponding to the dynamics of the scene. The actors' movements from one room to the other were orchestrated to guide the audience's gaze and emphasise the narrative transitions. In addition, impactful sounds, such as

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screams and voice changes, were used to reinforce this immersion, allowing the spectator to follow the evolution of the scene even through the physical separation of the actors.

3. Procedure

The test session took place in two distinct phases. First, each group was taken in turn to the corridor adjacent to the two rooms to observe the scene. Following each observation, the participants were asked to complete a questionnaire lasting around ten minutes. Throughout the experiment, the participants were positioned in the corridor, standing in front of the doors of the two rooms (Fig.1). They were allowed to move from one door to the other in the corridor but were not allowed to enter the rooms. Their only responsibility was to observe the scene carefully. In addition, they were forbidden to communicate with each other from the start of the observation of the scene until all the participants (in both groups) had finished answering the questionnaire. Each group was filmed during the scene so that their behaviour could be analysed.

The semi-directive questionnaire developed for this experiment was of crucial interest insofar as it made it possible to evaluate several key aspects linked to the perception and understanding of a scenarised scene between two distinct and adjacent spaces. Firstly, it provides an assessment of the participants' cognitive ability to grasp and interpret the elements of the environment presented to them. This includes their ability to semantise the environment, i.e. to attribute meaning to the various elements in the scene, as well as their ability to understand the situational logic and to anticipate the events taking place.

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Secondly, the questionnaire was specifically designed to examine the quality of the participants' memories, particularly their short-term memory, by asking them to describe the narrative, the characters and the events that took place in front of them. This assessment was essential for understanding how information is processed and remembered in a natural context, important data to compare with how participants processed and remembered what they saw in VR headsets.

In addition, the questionnaire aimed to determine whether participants encountered difficulties in following the narrative between the two rooms and to identify which aspects they found most complex, which can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the staging and transition between narrative elements.

Finally, by asking participants to identify the moments they consider most important in the scene, the questionnaire provides insights into the narrative elements that capture their attention and interest the most. Again, this information can be used to optimise the design of immersive experiences to maximise engagement and impact on the audience.

The participants were explicitly informed that there were no correct or incorrect answers, and that the aim of the experiments was not to assess their mental capacities, but to test new approaches to storytelling adapted to immersive devices such as virtual reality headsets.

4. Thursday May 16th, 2024: The participants

For the second experiment, a sample of 10 students, different from the first experiment, 5 enrolled in the first and second years of the ICCD course of the Master's programme in Information-Communication at the Université Côte d'Azur, and 5 enrolled in the first year of the MSC Sound Design, was selected. The sample was made up of 2 women and 8 men, 7 of whom were aged between 18 and 25, 2 between 26 and 35 and 1 over 35. Following the same model, the students were divided into two groups of 5: 5 ICCD students ('creative' group) and 5 MSC Sound Design students ('non-creative' group), who had voluntarily taken part in the 'spherical-scene perception' experiment. None of the students received any compensation (ECTS credits or remuneration) for their participation.

5. Protocol group

Mr Sobieszczanski and I made up the protocol group. The roles were the same as in the 'natural perception' experiment.

6. Stimuli

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Two videos of the same scene played by the same two actors in the same rooms, filmed in 360° on April 10th, 2024, and lasting 4 minutes and 14 seconds, were played in the VR headsets (*Meta Quest 2 and 3*). The participant observes two separate videos in the headset: the video from the point of view of room 1 and the video from the point of view of room 2. In each video, the viewer is given a glimpse of what is happening in the adjacent room by the overlay of a video in equirectangular format at door level.

7. Procedure

The two phases of the test session were broadly similar to those of the first experiment. Each participant in each group viewed the scene in the VR headsets (Fig.2), followed by the completion of a questionnaire lasting around ten minutes. Their task was also to observe the scene carefully. They were allowed to move their heads and turn around to look around. In line with the previous experiment on natural perception, any form of communication between the participants in the two groups was forbidden from the start of the visualisation until all the participants had completed the questionnaire. We recorded the mirroring of the content broadcast through the headsets to a few participants from both groups, to enable us to analyse their movements as they followed the narration.

The semi-directive questionnaires drawn up for this experiment were designed to replicate the questions posed in the natural perception questionnaire, with a focus on various critical aspects of perception and comprehension of a scripted scene between two distinct boundary spaces. Specifically, it probed the quality of memories and the identification of difficulties encountered.

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However, it incorporated inquiries regarding the VR headset device, this time, seeking to establish the participants' prior familiarity with VR headsets, including their frequency and context of use. Secondly, it explored the comfort (or discomfort) associated with watching videos while wearing the headset, as well as the physical and sensory experiences of wearing the device itself. This included an analysis of the influence of the headset's weight and associated symptoms, such as cyberkinetosis or cybersickness (including symptoms such as paleness, feeling unwell, visual disturbances, headaches, fatigue, nausea, dizziness, disorientation or tachycardia), sensory incongruence, and other factors, on users' reception and understanding of the scene. Ultimately, the questionnaire sought to elucidate how these factors shape participants' relationship with the presented scene.

Understanding how participants relate to VR headsets enables us to assess their degree of acclimatisation to the interface and immersion offered by VR headsets. This knowledge has significant implications for assessing the impact of VR headsets on users' reception of presented content, as well as their behavioral responses and interactions, which are often manifested through bodily movements, and allow us to draw a link of causal influence. This also enables the establishment of a correlation between participants' familiarity with the device and the incidence of adverse symptoms, which affect a substantial proportion of users (ranging from 30% to 50%). Notably, these symptoms have been found to vary as a function of demographic factors, such as age and gender (with males comprising the majority of VR headset users), as well as the type of content presented (e.g., rollercoaster versus forest walk) and the degree of visual field stimulation (Attia, D., 2021).

The responses and data collected in this context will facilitate a more nuanced understanding of the ergonomic considerations involved in scripting content for head-mounted displays. Once again, it is noteworthy that participants were explicitly assured that their responses would not be subject to value judgments, and that the primary objective of the study was to investigate novel methods of scripting tailored to immersive technologies, such as virtual reality headsets, without attempting to evaluate their mental capacities.

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8. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

1. Results from April 17th, 2024

When we first analyse the answers to the quantitative questions, we observe a significant disparity in the way in which the participants in the 'creative' group (ICCD students) and the 'non-creative' group (DISTIC students) approach the understanding of the scene. In response to the question 'To what extent do you think you have memorised the actions that took place in front of you?', the majority of the 'non-creative' participants (three out of five participants) indicated that they had memorised 'the majority of the actions'. However, two of them expressed a degree of uncertainty, believing that they had memorised 'most of the actions'. The 'creative' participants were more confident, with four out of five believing they had memorised 'the majority of the actions' and only one believing they had memorised 'most of the actions'. Although this difference does not seem significant enough to suggest that the 'creative' participants had a better grasp of their understanding of the scene than the 'non-creative' participants, their responses to the following questions nevertheless confirm this trend. In response to the question 'Did you find it difficult to follow the sequence of events between the two plays?', the trend is confirmed with all the 'non-creative' participants admitting that they found it difficult 'at times' to follow the narrative. On a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents the highest level of difficulty and 5 the lowest, two participants rated these difficulties at 4/5 and three at 3/5. Overall, although these participants felt that they had memorised the scene as a whole, they admitted that they had encountered difficulties. When we asked them to explain their difficulties, their answers were unanimous: following the narrative is difficult when it is distributed between two spaces, even concurrent ones, and with the possibility of moving around.

On the other hand, the 'creative' participants were again more confident. Three of them said that they had 'sometimes' found it difficult to follow the events, while two said that they had not encountered any difficulties. On a scale of 1 to 5, two participants rated difficulties at 3/5, one at 1/5, one at 4/5 and one at 5/5. However, it is reasonable to assume that the participant who gave a score of 1/5 made a mistake by reversing the values on the scale. In fact, this same participant had initially answered 'No' to the question on the difficulty of following the course of events between the two rooms, which suggests an evaluation of the difficulty at 5/5. We therefore interpret his answer as an evaluation of the difficulty at 5/5: thus, the 'creative' group includes two participants who evaluated the difficulty at 3/5, one at 4/5, and two at 5/5. Once again, when we asked the three participants who admitted to having had difficulties 'at times' to describe them,

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their answers varied. One of the 'creative' participants echoed the feelings of the 'non-creative' participants, explaining that following the narrative distributed between the two pieces made it difficult to understand (and remember). Another mentioned that the difficulties encountered were not linked to the narrative but to the space itself, particularly the narrowness of the doors, which prevented a view of the events taking place inside the rooms, given the number of participants present in the corridor. The last participant, meanwhile, mentioned the fact of 'maintaining vision between the two rooms and the two actions at the same time'. These last two responses are of particular interest, as they will later provide opportunities to analyse the reactions, interactions and behaviours of the participants to the scene unfolding before them.

An initial analysis can already be made, with the results revealing several significant trends. Firstly, the 'creative' participants showed greater confidence in their ability to memorise and understand the actions on stage than the 'non-creative' participants. This confidence was reflected in their responses to the question about memorising events, where most 'creative' participants felt they had memorised the majority of actions, in contrast to 'non-creative' participants who expressed more varied levels of confidence. In addition, the 'non-creative' participants reported more frequent and greater difficulties, whereas the 'creative' participants presented more variable levels of difficulty, but overall, less pronounced. The reasons given for these difficulties also differed between the two groups, highlighting a different approach to their experience when observing the scene, and suggesting other elements to consider, particularly concerning the participants' spatial interactions with the scene, which we will analyse last.

Let's now look at the answers to the qualitative questions. First, we need to consider that the main elements necessary for an overall understanding of the narrative lie in the fact that Mrs Doubtfire's role is a double role (Mrs Doubtfire is both Daniel), that the scene is based on this deception and that it is eventually revealed. Other important elements punctuate this scene and guide the narrative between the two plays: Daniel/Mrs Doubtfire changes roles multiple times and alternates between the two characters, the narrative takes place in two separate and concurrent rooms, the two characters are injured during the play and Daniel/Doubtfire is eventually unmasked.

We asked both groups to briefly describe the story they had just observed, to understand what elements of the narrative they had understood and retained. When we look at the responses from the 'non-creative' participants, we can see that all five understood the dual role of Mrs Doubtfire/Daniel, the central point of the scenario. Four of them understood that Mrs Doubtfire was initially a man and mentioned the gender change. Their answers included 'a man pretends to be a woman', 'a person who welcomes a woman into his or her home', 'the person who invites plays

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two people, one of whom is an old lady' and 'the man plays two roles, his own and that of a woman [...] he dresses in accessories to feminise himself'. However, only two of them mentioned the plot twist (Mrs Sellner reveals Daniel's deception) and the distributed narration, which includes 'the room on the right' and 'the other room'. In addition, two participants mentioned the family relationship between Mrs. Doubtfire and Daniel (half-brother and sister) shown in the scene, one of whom expressed doubt about the nature of their supposed bond: 'The man is telling the story of his sister or [of] his mother-in-law, I'm not sure'.

In the 'creative' group, the participants also unanimously understood the dual role and four of them understood that Mrs Doubtfire was initially a man and mentioned the gender change (tied with the 'non-creative' participants): 'The man is disguised as a woman', '[he] passes himself off as his mother', 'The story of a man who passes himself off as his sister', 'A man has disguised himself as a woman'. Three participants (compared to two 'non-creatives') mentioned the final scene and only one participant (compared to two 'non-creatives') specified that the scene took place between two rooms: 'The man switches rooms to change clothes'. Three participants (compared to two 'non-creatives') mentioned the family link between Mrs Doubtfire and Daniel, one of whom also expressed a doubt similar to the 'non-creative' participant: 'his mother or sister'. However, we can hypothesise that this confusion between mother and sister may be caused by two factors: the first being the actors' accents and the second being that the Doubtfire character is older (older than Daniel).

Thus, in terms of narrative comprehension, there was no significant difference between the two groups, although the 'non-creative' participants expressed greater difficulty in memorising and following the story than the 'creative' participants. Both groups used a similar lexical field associated with deception and impersonation, with expressions such as 'make believe' and 'pretend', indicating a common understanding of storytelling. Perhaps we can note that two 'non-creative' participants noticed the two distinct environments and their impact on storytelling, compared to only one 'creative' participant, suggesting a potential difference in sensitivity to this dimension echoing the 'non-creative' responses about their difficulty in following the narrative between these two spaces. However, given the statistical insignificance of this observation, this interpretation remains unconvincing. There was, however, a difference in the incorporation of narrative details into the description of the narrative. Both groups memorised various details of the story, including the context, events and characters, but these elements differed between the groups. For example, two participants in the 'non-creative' group identified the two rooms as being used as Daniel/Doubtfire's home by using the expression 'at home', while another participant specifically mentioned a 'flat'. In addition, one of the participants who used the expression 'at

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home' also remembered and identified Doubtfire as 'an old lady'. Another participant described the fact that the actor playing Doubtfire/Daniel changes characters in the second room by 'taking off a disguise and putting it back on later' and mentioned the fact that both characters are injured during the scene. In particular, he described the final scene: 'When actor B was injured, actor A ran into the room and realised that he was pretending to be several people. That was the end of the play'. So, the details that caught the attention of the 'non-creative' participants were based more on the context of the scene (where are we?) and the events.

The 'creative' participants retained fewer details. None of the 'creative' participants mentioned injuries or described the exact sequence of events. The details retained also relate to the context, but this time on the reasons for Daniel's deception: 'A man disguised himself as a woman to make an examiner believe that he lived with his sister', 'a man who invited a friend to his home, making her believe that his mother or sister was also there', 'a man who pretended to be his sister because she was absent in front of a lady who came to visit him'. Unlike the 'non-creative' group, the 'creative' participants provided more details about the characters (their roles, their emotions): while the 'non-creatives' described the character of Mrs Sellner as a simple 'woman', two 'creatives' described her, one as an 'inspector' and the other as an 'examiner', while a third described her as a 'friend'. The latter described Daniel as 'overwhelmed' by events, which led his 'friend' to discover the deception.

What can be deduced from this difference in terms of remembering and interpreting the details of a story is that it highlights the different ways in which the 'creative' and 'non-creative' groups prioritise what is an integral part of the narrative. The 'non-creative' participants focus more on the concrete/primary aspects such as context and events, while the 'creative' participants tend to provide fewer factual details but already begin a second reading/understanding of the narrative by focusing on the characters' motivations and emotional nuances.

To further assess the memorisation of details, particularly concerning the course of events and the characters, the two groups answered other questions: 'Can you briefly describe the events (actions) you observed?' and 'Can you briefly describe the characters (name, characteristics, character, etc.)?' To assess how the narration had affected their memory, they were asked what they considered to be the most important/memorable moments in the story, and to justify their comments. All the participants in the 'non-creative' group described the events and actions that had been put in place to guide the narrative between the rooms and that had made important noises : all mentioned the tea (which led to a burning followed by a scream), three mentioned the

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mouse trap (which made a popping noise followed by a scream) and four mentioned the sticky (which led to a jostling, never mentioned by any of the participants in either group).

The 'creative' participants, on the other hand, gave much less detailed and less complete descriptions of the actions guiding attention. None mentioned the mouse trap, although five did mention tea and changing gender (as did the 'non-creative' participants), and four the sticky. However, in the majority of participants' responses we again find attention focused on details, such as the specific behaviours of the characters, which we do not find in the "non-creative" participants: we find "The woman observes the room", "the man greets his friend", "the woman takes notes", "the woman asking for sugar", "a man explaining his life and where he comes from", "the woman [...] gradually becomes [suspicious] [because of] the objects".

This tendency to memorise details linked to their own interpretation of the narrative was confirmed when the participants described the characters. On the one hand, the 'non-creative' participants either described the appearance of the characters, or linked them to the objects they used or their behaviour during the scene: 'a girl guest, with a notebook', 'a person who changes sex', 'a person dressed in black and white trousers with a blue notebook + pen, wanting to find out what's in the room [...] The other person disguises herself as a lady with swollen breasts [...] a high-pitched voice', 'a curly blonde wig and fake breasts'. Only one 'non-creative' participant described the characters as he perceived/interpreted them. Adjectives included 'smiling', 'talkative', 'bitter', 'clumsy' and 'very energetic'.

On the other hand, the 'creative' participants, most of whom (four out of five) described either the characters or the roles and relationships of the characters. The role of 'inspector' and the 'brother, sister' relationship were mentioned twice, along with adjectives such as 'burlesque', 'stressed', 'serious', 'suspicious', 'confused', 'extravagant', 'funny' and 'simple'.

When participants from both groups were asked to identify the most significant moments in the story, a convergence in their responses was observed, with the majority highlighting Daniel's transformations, the revelation of the deception and the incidents involving the mouse trap and the tea. However, a dissimilarity again emerged when they were asked to justify their choices, highlighting a persistent distinction between the two groups in the way they interpreted and semantised narrative elements. The justification for the memorable moments chosen by the 'non-creative' group focused, in many cases, on the impact of the actions on the unfolding of the plot. One participant even explained: 'the physical actions are more memorable than the dialogue. The key moments I remember are those where the action was strongest, where there was speed'.

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Only one 'non-creative' participant mentioned that the plot had had an emotional impact on his perception and memory, speaking of 'controversial emotions' aroused by the suspense of the plot.

Among the 'creative' participants, one said that it was the anticipation of the revelation of the imposture at the start of the scene that had made the moment of revelation memorable. This anticipation is a feeling of expectation stimulated by the plot (like suspense). Another participant described Daniel's transformations, the mouse trap incident and the plot twist as humorous ('funny') moments. Another described Daniel's transformations and the revelation as 'entertaining' and spoke of an 'interesting twist'. Only one 'creative' participant pointed out that it was the actions that generated noise, such as the shouting and banging, that captured his attention.

What can we conclude from these responses? Firstly, there was convergence in the moments considered most significant, such as Daniel's transformations, the revelation of the deception and the incidents involving the mouse trap and the tea, regardless of the group to which the participants belonged. However, when we examine the justifications for these choices, some important distinctions emerge. Non-creative' participants tend to remember and give importance to the events that make up the action. It is through the perception of these events that they will understand the narrative and then memorise it. On the other hand, 'creative' participants attach more importance to the emotional aspect and complexity of the plot, expressing expectations raised by the plot, as well as an appreciation for the humorous and entertaining elements of the story. They are already in a more advanced stage of 'information processing' than the 'non-creative' participants. While the visual perception of 'non-creative' participants focuses essentially on the development of mental schemas for understanding the environment, 'creative' participants seem to master the environment more quickly and easily, and thus begin a process of memorisation and semantisation that can be modulated by emotional states.

A final relevant aspect to examine concerns the behaviour shown by the observers in front of the scene and their way of observing the distributed narrative. Let's start with the behaviours common to both groups. First, let's look at the behaviours shared by the two groups. Firstly, the participants in both groups showed emotional reactions to the scene: they smiled, laughed, and expressed their astonishment by widening their eyes or exchanging furtive glances with each other throughout the event, with variations in these reactions depending on the events occurring in the scene and its comic aspect. Thus, the theatrical performance elicited emotional responses in both groups, although these appear to have had a more significant impact on memorization and semantic comprehension in the 'creative' participants, as revealed by their responses to the questionnaire.

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Then, while some participants remained motionless for most of the performance despite being able to move around the corridor, we observe that at the end of the scene some of them chose to move around to optimise their view of the rooms, particularly during the final revelation when Mrs Sellner discovers that Mrs Doubtfire and Daniel are the same person. The fact that these participants decided to move towards the end of the scene, particularly at the crucial moment of the final revelation, indicates a recognition of the importance of this element in the overall unfolding of the play, which they indicated in the questionnaire. Thus, the choice to move at this point reflects a conscious strategy on the part of the participants to better apprehend and appreciate the denouement of the story and testifies to the spectators' commitment and active involvement in the theatrical narrative.

The major divergence in behaviour between the two groups lay in their approach to optimising their observation of the scene shared between the two plays. The 'non-creative' participants showed a tendency to move around the corridor to alternate their vision between room 1 and room 2. Their movements were characterised either by body movements or by head and eye movements. However, only two of the 'creative' participants adopted a similar strategy based on body movements. The other three participants preferred another approach: they positioned themselves between the two rooms in order to have a view of both spaces simultaneously, by slightly adjusting their head or eyes.

To put in a nutshell, the analysis of the responses to the questionnaire on the 'natural perception' experience, coupled with the observation of the participants' behaviours, makes it possible to initiate a reflection on the way in which "creative" and "non-creative" individuals approach their own understanding of a new narrative, outside the standards of conventional theatre and cinema. In view of the overall results, we can already assume a relationship between creativity and the perception, memorisation and understanding of the events observed when a script differs from standard codes.

8. Results from May 16th, 2024

The questionnaires administered to the participants in the May 16th experiment included questions about their familiarity with the device, their comfort and the symptoms associated with its use, with the aim of assessing the influence of these factors on the reception of the content. We will therefore begin by analysing these aspects. Firstly, although we might initially assume that 'creative' participants would have used a VR headset more frequently than 'non-creative' ones, the results reveal similar trends between the two groups. Indeed, to the question 'Have you ever

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used a VR headset' (before the experiment), four out of five 'non-creative' participants answered 'yes', compared to three 'creative' participants. However, in answer to the question 'How often?', we can see that the 'creative' participants who had already used a VR headset had used it several times and more frequently: two of the 'creative' participants had therefore used a VR headset 'more than 10 times', one of whom said he had used it 'from time to time' and the other 'very often' over the last 6 months. The third 'creative', who had already used a VR headset between '5 and 10 times', said they had used it 'rarely' in the last 6 months.

Among the 'non-creatives', the number of uses and frequency is less significant and more disparate. One participant had used a VR headset more than 10 times, another had used it '5 to 10 times', yet another '2 or 3 times' and the last had only used it 'once'. However, all four participants had almost never used a VR headset in the last 6 months: participants who had used a VR headset '5 to 10 times' and '2 or 3 times' felt that they had 'never' used a VR headset in the last 6 months, while participants who had used a VR headset 'more than 10 times' and 'only once' felt that they had 'rarely' used one in the last 6 months. They were asked two questions about the context of their use of the device. The first question concerned the overall context of use of the helmet. Among all the participants in both groups, the three contexts mentioned most often were video games (Beat Saber, Space Pirate and VR Chat), cultural experiences in the context of museums and immersive cultural and creative experiences outside museums (cinema, music and virtual visits were mentioned). When asked about the contexts in which the VR headset has been used in the last 6 months, we can see that video games are still the big winner (three out of five participants in both groups mention this), followed by cultural events (two out of five participants in both groups mention 'museum' and 'immersive experience').

We can already conclude that although the two groups have already experienced VR headsets at least once, with no significant difference (four 'non-creative' versus only three 'creative', mainly digital natives), the 'creative' group have used the device more often and more frequently. We also noted that the content most consumed in virtual reality was video games (including VR Chat) and cultural content in the context of museums or various immersive experiences (virtual tours, artistic content, music). However, it is important to point out a potential bias. Among the 'creative' participants, two had never used a VR headset. However, as the participants are students in the ICCD master's programme, they are used to creating and viewing 360° content without actually using headsets. It is therefore essential to highlight the 'creative' participants' ease with immersive digital technologies (including the creation of content for digital devices) even if they have not experienced the VR headset.

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Let's now look at the possibility of a link between the frequency of use of the device by participants in the two groups and the comfort (or discomfort) associated with wearing the headset. Participants were asked to rate comfort on a scale of 1 to 5 (5 being considered 'very comfortable') after watching the first video, and again after watching the second video. They were also asked whether they found the headset heavy after the first viewing, and whether it felt heavier (or lighter) after the second viewing. Overall, the 'creative' participants felt more comfortable wearing the headset. They found it quite comfortable, giving an average score of 4/5, and light, since they unanimously answered 'no' to the question 'Did you find the headset heavy' After the second viewing, the 'creative' participants felt that their experience of wearing the headset remained the same, both in terms of comfort and weight.

The 'non-creative' participants were less comfortable overall, giving an average rating of 3.6/5 for comfort. However, most of them did not find the headset heavy (only one 'non-creative' participant said he found it heavy). After the second viewing, comfort dropped slightly from 3.6/5 to 3.4/5, with one participant finding it heavier and one finding it lighter.

After the comfort questions, the participants answered various questions relating to cyber kinetosis. They were asked if they had experienced headaches, dizziness or nausea and eye strain. If participants answered 'yes', they were asked to rate their experience on a scale of 1 to 5 (5 being 'very painful'). After the first viewing, the 'non-creative' participants were the only ones to experience symptoms related to wearing the headphones: three out of five participants experienced mild headaches (with an average intensity of 2/5), four out of five participants experienced mild dizziness or nausea (with an average intensity of 2.75/5) and four out of five participants experienced mild eye strain (with an average intensity of 2.25/5). The most intense symptoms were nausea/vertigo. It is important to note, however, that the only 'non-creative' participant who did not experience any symptoms was the participant who had used a VR headset more than 10 times, even though he had used one only rarely in the last 6 months. The 'creative' participants did not experience any symptoms.

They were asked the same questions again after the second viewing, to assess whether their condition had improved or worsened. Thus, even after the second viewing and with a break of around ten minutes between the two viewings, the 'non-creative' participants were still the ones experiencing the most symptoms. However, their condition improved markedly: only one participant experienced headaches, but with greater intensity (1/5 after the first viewing, and 4/5 after the second). This same participant was the only one to experience nausea/vertigo, which again worsened (2/5 after the first viewing, then 3/5 after the second). Two participants

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experienced eye fatigue, which also worsened (an average of 2/5 after the first viewing compared with an average of 3/5 after the second). Once again, the 'non-creative' participant who used a VR headset more than 10 times did not experience any symptoms after the second viewing. However, on the other hand, a 'creative' participant reported experiencing a single symptom, which was eye fatigue of intensity 3/5 after the second viewing.

To conclude the 'familiarity and comfort of wearing the helmet' section, participants were asked two final questions: 'Overall, would you say that wearing the headset interfered with your experience' and 'How would you describe your experience with the headset', which were repeated after the second viewing. While two 'non-creative' participants 'agreed' that the headset detracted from their experience, the majority felt the opposite (two 'disagreed' and the participant who had used a VR headset more than 10 times 'disagreed at all'). The 'creative' participants unanimously felt that wearing the headset did not detract from their experience. After the second viewing, all the participants in both groups remained in the same position.

Despite symptoms and a headset that bothered them overall, the majority of 'non-creative' participants described the experience as 'quite immersive' (three answered 'quite immersive' and two 'immersive', again including the one with a high level of familiarity with VR headsets). However, it was the 'creative' participants who were more receptive to the experiment, with the majority describing the experience as 'immersive' (four out of five participants), including one who described it as 'very immersive'.

After the second viewing, two 'non-creative' participants felt 'less immersed' and only one 'more immersed' than after the first viewing. The two 'non-creative' participants who felt less immersed were the two whose symptoms persisted after the second viewing. As for the 'creative' participants, one of them felt more immersed and another less so. However, this reduced sense of immersion was not correlated with symptoms experienced after the second viewing.

In conclusion, the answers to these questions in the two questionnaires make it possible to establish a link between familiarity with the VR headset, the comfort associated with wearing it and the way in which the experience is 'felt' (more or less immersion). We were able to highlight that although both groups had previous experience with VR headsets, the 'creative' group felt more comfortable overall during the viewing sessions and had a more positive perception than the 'non-creative' group. The only exception was the 'non-creative' group who were familiar with the device, as they were the only ones to experience no symptoms and to feel comfortable with the headset, while describing the experience as 'immersive'. Previous experience with the device

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therefore seems to play a protective role both in terms of symptoms and the perception of immersion.

Let's now look at how participants in the two groups perceived their ability to memorise the scene. When asked 'How well do you think you remembered the actions that took place in front of you', the majority of the 'non-creative' participants were less confident than the 'creative' participants. Three said they had memorised 'most of the actions' and two said they had memorised 'some of the actions'. As for the 'creative' participants, two indicated that they had memorised 'the majority of the actions', two 'most of the actions' and only one expressed some doubts, indicating that they had memorised only 'some of the actions'. In the questionnaire submitted after the second viewing, they were asked the same question. This second exposure enabled the 'non-creative' participants to regain their confidence: two said they had memorised 'most of the actions', two others 'the majority of the actions' and only one said he had remembered nothing at all.

For the 'creative' participants, the trend was also upwards, but less significantly than for the 'non-creative' participants, since only one changed his answer to indicate that he had 'memorised everything'.

Both questionnaires asked them about their difficulty in following the course of events during the scene. In the first questionnaire, they were asked to rate, on a scale of 1 to 5 (5 being 'very easy'), how difficult it was to follow the course of events. The 'non-creative' participants gave an average score of 3.4/5, meaning that the events were generally easy to follow. While the 'creative' participants seemed to be the most at ease until now, the trend is now reversed, as they gave an average score of 3.2/5. We can therefore deduce that the 'creative' group, although confident, found it more difficult to follow the events than the 'non-creative' group. There is one important point to note, however: although the average is 0.2 points lower, the 'creative' group gave more marks close to 5: three of them gave a 4/5, one a 3 and the last a 1. It is this 1 that causes the average to fall drastically. If we calculate a median rather than an average, thereby eliminating the extreme values and expressing a value that is more representative of the groups, we obtain a median of 3/5 for the responses of the 'non-creatives', and a median of 4 for the responses of the 'creatives'. This gives a fairer balance between the two groups and is more consistent with the answers to the previous question. Participants in both groups were given the opportunity to specify the type of difficulty they had encountered. The answers were similar and highlighted a major problem: the difficulty of following events/actions that are taking place rapidly (as in a real situation, with no editing to punctuate the actions) and simultaneously. In short, the difficulty lies above all in

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deciding how to prioritise our gaze, which means accepting that we may 'miss' elements of the set or the actions/movements of other characters outside our field of vision.

In the second questionnaire, the 'non-creative' participants found the task simpler, with a median of 4/5 on the scale used to assess the difficulty of following up actions. The answers of the 'creative' participants obtained a median of 4/5. The medians therefore highlight the one-point improvement in the assessment of the 'non-creative' participants, who found the exercise simpler after the second viewing. However, the median for the 'creative' participants did not change. Nevertheless, can we really think that the 'progression' of the 'non-creative' participants is caused by an adaptation to the device and the type of content? When they explained the reasons why the exercise had become simpler, two 'non-creative' participants explained that there was less action and fewer set elements in the second video (showing the point of view of the second room where Daniel/Doubtfire carries out his transformations) than in the first (showing the point of view of the first room where Daniel and Mrs Sellner interact). The room was therefore 'emptier' than the first, and another element came into play: the presence of the flat inlay (in equirectangular view) to which two 'non-creative' participants referred. None of the 'creative' participants mentioned this overlay. The other factor that played a simplifying role was the fact of having observed the same scene twice. This was mentioned by two 'creative' participants who found the exercise simpler, and by only one 'non-creative' participant.

Once again, we can draw some conclusions from our observations. It would seem that the participants' familiarity with the device has a particular impact on the way they apprehend their own memory capacity. The 'creative' participants were more confident than their 'non-creative' peers, who found the exercise more difficult and therefore doubted their ability to memorise a scene they found complex. However, after a second viewing, the responses of the 'non-creative' participants showed an increase in confidence and a decrease in their estimation of the difficulty. This 'progression' was not present (or only to a limited extent) among the 'creative' participants, who felt no significant change between the first and second viewings. We can deduce from this that, when individuals are introduced to the system or to new types of 360° content, their 'cognitive progression' is less obvious than that of a novice participant. The main difficulty, however, is shared by members of both groups: it is difficult to prioritise the view and to accept 'missing' elements. It is therefore easier, since we have absorbed the standard cinematographic codes, to follow an action (or a narrative) when it is isolated from any external distraction or when the image is in 2D.

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By looking at the answers to the qualitative questions, we can now see whether the participants' feelings are reflected in their transcription of the scene. As in the experiment on 17 April, all the participants were asked to briefly describe the story, the actions and the characters they had just observed. All the participants in both groups mentioned the dual role and the change of gender. On the 'creative' side we find: 'the man disguised as a woman', 'he changed his tone of voice (man and woman)' and 'he pretended to be his sister' (twice). On the 'non-creative' side, we find: 'he pretends to be a woman', 'a man cross-dresses', 'the man plays a woman' and 'the man is disguised as a woman'. Four 'creative' participants mentioned the narrative punchline: 'is unmasked by the woman', 'the inspector [...] sees that in the end there is only one person', 'the woman discovers her double game'. In the 'non-creative' group, four participants also mentioned it: 'she [the inspector] enters the second room and finds the half- man half-woman', 'the secretary surprises him', 'his deception is revealed'. Two 'creatives' mentioned the distributed narration, describing 'he goes into a separate room to change' and 'the man moves from one room to another', while three 'non-creatives' described 'the change of character takes place in a different room', 'the man returns to room 2 to change into a woman' and 'two roles from one room to another'. We note that while only one 'creative' mentioned the distribution of actions and justified why, this was the case for all the 'non-creatives' who mentioned the distributed narration. To continue with the important events in the scenario, the majority of participants in both groups (three 'creative' participants out of five, and four 'non- creative' participants out of five) mentioned the injuries suffered by the characters during the scene. Two creatives mentioned Daniel's burn and fall, and another referred to the action where Mrs Sellner 'hits herself' (actually getting a mouse trap in her foot). The 'non-creatives' mentioned 'falling', the verb 'to fall' twice, 'burns himself with a cup of tea' and 'hurts himself'.

Overall, we can see that participants in both groups understood the important events in the scene. However, there was a difference in the memorisation of various details of the scenario, including the context, the events and the characters. In fact, the 'creative' group remembered more details overall than the 'non-creative' group. We can cite a few responses to illustrate this point. Firstly, two 'creative' participants identified the location as a 'flat', which was not the case for any of the 'non-creative' participants. The difference in terms of memorisation is then accentuated on the details related to the characters. Two 'creative' participants mentioned the family relationship between Daniel and Doubtfire 'he pretends to be his sister' (twice), and then correctly identified Mrs Sellner's role, describing her as an 'inspector'. Only one 'non-creative' identified the family link ('brother') and two identified Mrs Sellner's role. However, one of them understood her to be an inspector, while the other participant described her first as a 'domestic' and then as a 'secretary'.

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However, the major discrepancy between the two groups was in the way they described the characters. Among the 'non-creatives', two mentioned the fact that the characters were English, one described Daniel as a 'clumsy man', and one described all the characters in detail: he remembered the first name 'Danny', described the inspector as 'cold' and curious, Doubtfire as 'bombastic and demonstrative' as well as 'wearing a lot of make-up' and Daniel as 'kind and clumsy'. Only two 'non-creative' participants used adjectives to describe the characters and only one provided a detailed description. Furthermore, it is important to note that the participant who provided the detailed description was not the 'non-creative' participant who was used to the device, but the one who had only used a VR headset once in his life. The descriptions of the characters written by the 'creative' participants were denser: one remembered the first name 'Danny' and another described the inspector as 'attentive' and 'observant' and Daniel/Doubtfire as 'stressed, anxious, agitated'. Yet another mentioned a pre-scene relationship between Mrs Sellner and Daniel ('the characters seem to know each other'), described Daniel as 'disorganised' and the inspector as 'serious' and dissatisfied with the meeting. A final participant incorporated physical details into the characters, describing 'a dark-haired man' with 'a blond wig' and a 'stern-looking' woman.

Not only did the 'creative' participants retain more details than the 'non-creative' participants, but they also incorporated these details when asked to transcribe the actions taking place in the scene, with two participants stating that Mrs Sellner was 'uncomfortable' and 'worried'.

When asked 'What were the most important or memorable moments in the story for you?', the majority of participants in both groups indicated firstly the revelation of the deception (final scene), then the actions that produced noise (the burning and the fall) and finally the double-cross. The main reason given for choosing the moment of revelation was that the secret was finally exposed, something that all the participants in all the groups seemed to be waiting for. With regard to the noisy actions and the double play, the responses once again diverged: the 'creative' participants stressed the importance of the sound that attracted their attention, while the 'non-creative' participants mentioned the movements of the characters. It should also be noted that only one of the ten participants, a 'creative', said that the noisy actions were 'funny'.

When we look at the recordings of the content broadcast through the headphones during the experiment, we see that all the participants, regardless of their familiarity with the device, follow the events with their eyes and move their gaze (by moving their head) from one character to another to follow the discussion. However, the 'creative' participants tended to move around more,

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turning around and looking up and down, than the 'non-creative' participants, who were more static. Discussion of the results from April 17th and May 16th, 2024, and conclusion.

Let's now compare our results. Did the participants in the two groups have the same understanding of their memory capacity during the 'natural perception' experiment and the 'spherical-scene' experiment? To answer this question, let's analyse the responses concerning the participants' confidence in their memory and the difficulties they encountered during the two sessions. First of all, let's compare the answers to the question: 'How well do you think you remembered the actions that took place in front of you? It appears that, overall, the participants felt more confident after the 'natural perception' experiment than after the 'spherical scene'¹ experiment. One likely hypothesis is that this difference in confidence can be attributed to the influence of the device used. It is possible that the VR headset had an intimidating or disruptive effect on the participants, thus affecting their perception of their memory abilities. However, it should be noted that, when we take into account the responses to the second questionnaire of the 'spherical scene' experiment, the results obtained are considerably closer to (but not equal to) the results obtained from the 'natural perception' experiment, which may reflect a gain in confidence and an adaptation to the headset device and the content broadcast within it.

Let's continue by looking in more detail at the responses relating to the difficulties encountered by the participants in each type of experiment. Evaluating these responses could give us further clues as to why 'natural perception' generated greater confidence in the 'spherical-scene' and whether our hypothesis is likely. And indeed, although the participants felt less confident during the experiment with the VR headsets, they nevertheless felt less difficulty in following the course of events² in the scene than during the 'natural perception' experiment. Let's compare the medians obtained: the scores given by the 'non-creative' group obtained a median of 3/5 (5 corresponds to 'very easy') for the 'natural perception' experiment. For the 'scene-sphere' experiment, the scores obtained a median value of 4/5. The 'non-creatives' therefore seem to have found it less difficult to

¹ In this section, are taken into account the participants' answers to the first questionnaire of the "spherical scene" session,

i.e. their first impressions after viewing video 1.

² Here, are assessed the participants' answers to the second questionnaire of the "spherical scene" session,

i.e. their final impressions after viewing video 2

(i.e. the scene from both points of view).

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follow the narrative distributed in the headsets than in natural perception. However, the difficulty expressed by the 'creatives' was unchanged (obtaining a median of 4/5 in both sessions). While the experience was the same for the 'creative' group, the 'non-creative' group rated the 360° experience as less difficult than the natural perception experience, the median having changed between the two questionnaires submitted during the second session. What can we deduce from this? The 'creatives' seem to be more at ease when faced with new scenarios and experiences (both in natural perception and in head-mounted perception). However, the difficulties faced by the 'non-creatives' diminish as they become more familiar with the device and the content, despite symptoms of cyberkinesia. Another observation: the participants gave reasons for their difficulties and, in both experiments, the difficulty that stands out most is that of prioritising the view. In fact, some participants from all groups said that it was difficult to follow events taking place simultaneously.

Let's compare the results of the two sessions in terms of extracting and remembering information, including details (context, location, characters, etc.). During the 'natural perception' experiment, the majority of the 'non-creative' group were able to describe the actions/events more accurately than the 'creative' group. Their attention was focused on the various events in the room and the actions that made significant noises: the burning with the tea and the mouse trap. They also mentioned the Daniel/Doubtfire metamorphoses and the injuries sustained by the characters. The 'creative' group, on the other hand, had not mentioned any injuries and had described the actions in less detail. They did, however, attach the same importance to Daniel/Doubtfire's transformations as the 'non-creative' group. Nevertheless, they focused their attention on other elements relating more to the behaviour of the characters, their profile and their interactions. During the 'spherical scene' experiment, the responses were balanced, with participants in both groups mentioning most of the injuries suffered by the characters and the same actions.

The most significant difference between the two groups, in both experiments, lay in the memorisation of details. In natural perception, two 'non-creative' participants were able to identify the rooms as a flat. As for the characters, most of the details remembered related to the physical appearance of the characters or to the objects used in the action. The 'creatives' had memorised the context of the scene (the reason for Mrs Sellner's visit) and the relational links between the characters. They had interpreted the characters. In VR perception, the trend was reversed, with the 'creatives' giving more detail to the actions, identifying rooms like a flat, identifying the roles of each character and the links between them. Their description of the characters was in line with the way they described them in natural perception, and therefore described the characters' characters and their feelings. It should also be noted that none of the participants remembered the characters'

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first names during the first experiment, but that two participants (one from each group) managed to remember the nickname “Danny” during the second experiment. In addition, more ‘non-creatives’ interpreted the characters in the ‘spherical scene’ experiment than in the ‘natural perception’ experiment.

These comparisons once again underline the fact that the ‘creative’ participants interpreted the narrative and the characters more deeply than the ‘non-creative’ participants, who only transcribed the ‘tangible’ elements for the most part, whatever the device. However, the ‘non-creative’ participants were more interpretative during the ‘spherical-scene’ experiment than during the ‘natural perception’ experiment. In addition, the participants were able to retain visual and auditory elements, as well as details, whether in the headset or in natural perception. Although there were discrepancies between the details memorised in the two sessions, and between the participants in the two groups, all the participants in both groups were able to understand the scene, and to retain the major events necessary for understanding the scene.

Let's continue our discussion by comparing the results to the question concerning the impact of the scene on the participants. When participants were asked to choose ‘what were the most important or memorable moments in the story’, the two groups combined chose the same scenes in both experiments: the revelation of the deception, the actions that produced noise (burning, falling, mouse trap) and Daniel's transformations. However, the recurrence of each of these events differed between the two experimental sessions. For example, more importance was given to the moment of revelation during the 360° experiment than during the natural perception experiment. This suggests that the scene broadcast through the headsets created a more intense sense of expectation (suspense) than the ‘dramatised’ scene. What's more, in the ‘natural perception’ experiment, Daniel's transformations were cited the most. In terms of potential emotional impact, the ‘creative’ group were the ones who had the most emotional reactions (laughter, smiles, expressions of surprise) and who described this in the questionnaire, although some of the ‘non-creative’ group also reacted but less significantly. However, it appears that the 360° experiment provoked fewer emotional responses, even among the ‘creative’ participants. How can this phenomenon be explained? Do the VR headset and the scene filmed in 360° inhibit emotional responses compared with natural perception? To answer this question, we need to take into account the biases involved in analysing viewers' behaviour in front of the scene. Firstly, the spectators in the ‘natural perception’ experiment, unlike those in the ‘stage-sphere’ experiment, do not wear headsets to hide their faces. It is therefore easier to observe their reactions, to capture their smiles and laughter, and in particular their eyes and expressions. Although the headset does not cover the mouth, it is still more difficult to read facial expressions without the presence of the

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eyes. Also, during the 'natural perception' experiment, the participants, divided into groups, interacted with each other, even if they could not communicate verbally. The looks they exchanged, and the observation of their peers' behaviour may have influenced the way they experienced and perceived the scene. However, the fact that the 'creatives' were able to perceive and understand the emotions of the characters (which they later transcribed) proves that even the spherical scene has the capacity to convey the emotions of the characters to the spectators. Secondly, we were able to see that the spectator's familiarity with the device influenced his or her perception, with the 'creative' spectators being better able to perceive and interpret the characters' emotions. Given this observation and the results of the 'spherical scene' experiment, we can assume that the more familiar the viewer is with 360° content and the device, the better they will be able to perceive, interpret and in turn feel the emotions transmitted by the narrative.

Other points to consider concern viewers' behaviour during viewing and their links with the events that have marked them. It is possible that these responses will enable us to detect a different way of perceiving the narrative according to natural perception and perception in VR headsets.

For the 'creative' participants, sound had less of an impact during the 'natural perception' experiment than during the 'spherical scene' experiment. The 'non-creatives', on the other hand, seemed to be attracted overall by the visual action in both experiments. The first sense to guide attention and narration in both cases (natural perception and perception in the headsets) seems to be sight. Then comes hearing, which helps/accompanies the visual action and reinforces the impact on the viewer. This hypothesis is supported by observations of spectators' behaviour during the experiments. In the 'natural perception' experiment, the spectators initially followed the narration according to the actors' movements and were then guided by the noisy sounds that told them that something was happening. In VR, the spectators followed the actors' movements to understand whether they should look at the room in which they were immersed or at the overlay in the other room. It was the noisy actions that then drew their attention to a particular event. In short, the visual topology of a scene guides the spectator through the space and the sounds guide him towards the precise events that should capture his attention. However, all the spectators in the 'spherical scene' experiment tended to focus more on the actions taking place in one room, by watching the overlay, whereas those in the 'natural perception' experiment tended to want to perceive both rooms at the same time (either by moving more between the two rooms or by standing back).

What can we conclude from all these analyses? Although significant differences were not observed in all the dimensions examined, the overall results indicate trends suggesting a

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relationship between creativity/familiarity with new types of content and the perception, memorisation and understanding of events observed when a script differs from standardised codes. This would imply learning and adaptation, both to new demonstration/projection devices and to new types of content (in this case 360°) and scripting. In our studies, 'creative' people have a more trained perception than 'non-creative' people. As a result, they are more confident in their memory capacity (perhaps feeling less apprehensive) and have better recall, including of details. As a result, they can create mental schemas more easily and in a more 'efficient' way. They can then semantize their environment and are able to adjust to it, even if it changes. In our case, the 'creatives' had no particular difficulty in following the narrative in two different spaces. The 'non-creatives', although less confident and having encountered more difficulties, were also able to do so. In the headsets, participants in both groups were able to follow the narrative and orientate themselves spatially and temporally in the 360° scene. As a result, all the individuals were able to interact with the scene by turning around to follow the events, and to locate and watch the overlay when the action was taking place in the adjacent room. All the participants were therefore able to acquire a global understanding of the scene, both in natural perception and in 'scene-sphere' perception. The major difference was that the 'creative' participants were able to go beyond these elementary cognitive schemas and continue their reading on an emotional level.

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9. SELECTION OF COMPARATIVE GRAPHS OF QUESTIONNAIRE RESULTS

'CREATIVE' group - Comparison of the difficulty experienced during the 'natural perception' and 'spherical-scene perception' experiments (5 = 'Very easy').

(Creatives) "Natural perception"

6. Sur une échelle de 1 à 5, notez la difficulté à suivre le déroulement des événements entre les deux pi...

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'NON-CREATIVE' group - Comparison of the difficulty experienced during the 'natural perception'

(Creatives) "Spherical-scene perception" (questionnaire 1)

16. Sur une échelle de 1 à 5, notez la difficulté à suivre le déroulement des événements entre les deux... and 'spherical-scene perception' experiments (5 = 'Very easy').

(Non-creatives) "Natural perception"

(Non-creatives) "Spherical-scene perception" (questionnaire 1)

16. Sur une échelle de 1 à 5, notez la difficulté à suivre le déroulement des événements entre les deux...

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'CREATIVE' group - Comparison of responses to the question 'To what extent do you think you remembered the actions that took place in front of you?' in the "natural perception" and "spherical-scene perception" experiments.

(Creatives) "Natural perception"

Nombre de 4. À quel point pensez-vous avoir mémorisé les actions qui se sont déroulées devant v...
 4 'I have memorised the majority of the actions and 1 'I have memorised most of the actions'

(Creatives) "Spherical-scene perception" (questionnaire 1)

Nombre de 14. À quel point pensez-vous avoir mémorisé les actions qui se sont déroulées devant...

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2 'I have memorised the majority of the actions', 2 'I have memorised most of the actions', 1 'I have memorised only some actions'

'NON-CREATIVE' group - Comparison of responses to the question 'How well do you think you remembered the actions that took place in front of you?' in the "natural perception" and "spherical-scene perception" experiments.

(Non-creatives) "Natural perception"

3 'I have memorised the majority of the actions and 2 'I have memorised most of the actions'

(Non-creatives) "Spherical-scene perception" (questionnaire 1)

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3 'I have memorised most of the actions' and 2 'I have memorised only some actions'

'NON-CREATIVE' group - Evolution of the difficulty felt between questionnaire 1 (after a first viewing) and 2 (after a second viewing) during the 'spherical-scene perception' experiment (5 = 'Very easy').

(Non-creatives) "Spherical-scene perception" (questionnaire 1)

16. Sur une échelle de 1 à 5, notez la difficulté à suivre le déroulement des événements entre les deux...

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'NON-CREATIVE' group - Comparison of responses to the question 'To what extent do you think

(Non-creatives) "Spherical-scene perception" (questionnaire 2)

13. Sur une échelle de 1 à 5, notez la difficulté à suivre le déroulement des événements entre les deux...
 you remembered the actions that took place in front of you?' between questionnaire 1 and
 2 during the 'spherical-scene perception' experiment.

(Non-creatives) "Spherical-scene perception" (questionnaire 1)

Nombre de 14. À quel point pensez-vous avoir mémorisé les actions qui se sont déroulées devant...

3 'I have memorised most of the actions' and 2 'I have memorised only some actions'

(Non-creatives) "Spherical-scene perception" (questionnaire 1)

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2 'I have memorised most of the actions', 2 'I have memorised the majority of the actions' and 1 'I didn't remember anything'

'NON-CREATIVE' group - Comparison of responses relating to symptoms of cyberkinetosis experienced between questionnaire 1 (after a first viewing) and 2 (after a second viewing).

(Non-creatives) Did you experience any headaches during/after viewing? (questionnaire 1)

Nombre de 8. Avez-vous ressenti des maux de têtes ou des migraines pendant/après le visionnage ?

3 'yes' and 2 'No'

(Non-creatives) Did you experience any headaches during/after viewing? (questionnaire 2)

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Nombre de 5. Avez-vous ressenti des maux de têtes ou des migraines pendant/après le visionnage ? 49

1 'yes' and 4 'No'

(Non-creatives) Did you feel dizzy, unbalanced or nauseous during/after watching the video ? (questionnaire 1)

Nombre de 9. Avez-vous ressenti des sensations de vertiges, de déséquilibre ou de nausées pend...

4 'yes' and 1 'No'

(Non-creatives) Did you feel dizzy, unbalanced or nauseous during/after watching the video ? (questionnaire 2)

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1 'yes' and 4 'No'

(Non-creatives) Did you experience eye strain after viewing?
(questionnaire 1)

Nombre de 10. Avez-vous ressenti une fatigue oculaire après le visionnage ?

4 'yes' and 1 'No'

(Non-creatives) Did you experience eye strain after viewing?
(questionnaire 2)

Nombre de 7. Avez-vous ressenti une fatigue oculaire pendant/après le visionnage ?

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2 'yes' and 3 'No'

2 'yes' and 3 'No'

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10. 'NATURAL PERCEPTION' EXPERIMENT QUESTIONNAIRE.

Your age

- 18-25 years old
- 26-35 years old
- over 35

Your gender

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Other
- I do not wish to answer

Your course of study

- DISTIC
- ICCD

How well do you think you remembered the actions that took place in front of you?

- I remembered nothing at all
- I only remembered some of the actions
- I remembered most of the actions
- I remembered the majority of the actions
- I remembered everything

On a scale of 1 to 5, rate how difficult it is to follow the sequence of events between the two pieces.

- 1 = very difficult / 5 = very easy

Did you find it difficult to follow the sequence of events between the two parts?

- Yes

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- At times
- No

(If yes or at times) What did you find difficult?

Can you briefly describe the scenario (story) you observed?

Can you briefly describe the events (actions) you observed?

Can you briefly describe the characters (names, characteristics, etc.)?

In your opinion, what are the most important or memorable moments in the story?

Why?

Is there anything else you would like to share about your experience?

Questionnaire 1, 'spherical-scene perception' experiment.

Your age

- 18-25 years old
- 26-35 years old
- over 35

Your gender

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Other
- I do not wish to answer

Your course of study

- Msc Sound Design
- ICCD

Your number

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- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

Have you ever used a VR headset?

- Yes
- No

If yes) How many times?

- 1 time only
- 2 or 3 times
- 5-10 times
- More than 10 times

In what context (video games, VR chat, museum, etc.)?

How often have you used a VR headset in the last 6 months?

- Never
- Rarely
- Once in a while
- Often
- Very often

(If other than never) In what context (video games, VR chat, museum, etc.)?

On a scale of 1 to 5, rate the comfort of wearing the headset.

- 1=Very uncomfortable / Very comfortable

Did you find the headset heavy?

- Yes
- No

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Did you experience any headaches or migraines during/after viewing?

- Yes
- No

(If yes) On a scale of 1 to 5, rate the intensity of these aches.

- 1 = Not very painful / 5 = Very painful

Did you feel dizzy, unbalanced or nauseous during the viewing?

- Yes
- No

(If yes) On a scale of 1 to 5, rate the intensity of these sensations.

- 1 = Very slight / 5 = Very intense

Did you experience eye strain after viewing?

- Yes
- No

(If yes) On a scale of 1 to 5, rate the intensity of this eye strain.

- 1 = Very mild / 5 = Very intense

If you have experienced other symptoms related to the use of the headset, please mention them below.

Overall, would you say that wearing a headset interfered with your experience?

- Totally agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- No agreement at all

How would you describe your experience with the headset?

- Very immersive

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- Immersive
- Quite immersive
- Not at all immersive

How well do you think you memorised the actions that took place in front of you?

- I remembered everything
- I remembered the majority of the actions
- I remembered most of the actions
- I only remembered some of the actions
- I remembered nothing at all

Did you find it difficult to follow the sequence of events between the two rooms?

- Yes
- At times
- No

(If yes or at times) What did you find difficult in following the sequence of events?

On a scale of 1 to 5, rate the difficulty of following the sequence of events between the two rooms.

- 1= Very difficult / 5= Very easy

Questionnaire 2, 'spherical-scene perception' experiment.

Your course

- MSc Sound Design
- ICCD

Your number

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

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After watching video 2, how would you describe the comfort of wearing a headset?

- It's more comfortable
- The comfort is the same
- I felt more discomfort

(If 'it's more comfortable' or 'I feel more discomfort') On a scale of 1 to 5, rate the comfort of wearing a helmet after watching video 2.

- 1= Very uncomfortable / 5= Very comfortable

Did the headset feel heavier?

- Yes
- No
- It seemed lighter

Did you experience any headaches during/after viewing?

- Yes
- No

(If yes) On a scale of 1 to 5, rate the intensity of these aches.

- 1 = Not very painful / 5 = Very painful

Did you feel dizzy, unbalanced or nauseous during the viewing?

- Yes
- No

(If yes) On a scale of 1 to 5, rate the intensity of these sensations.

- 1= Very mild / 5= Very intense

Did you experience eye strain after viewing?

- Yes
- No

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(If yes) On a scale of 1 to 5, rate the intensity of this eye strain.

- 1=very mild / 5=very intense

If you have experienced other symptoms related to the use of the headset, please mention them below.

After watching video 2, would you say that wearing the headset interfered with your experience?

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- No agreement at all

After watching video 2, how would you describe your experience with the headset?

- I felt more immersed
- My experience was unchanged
- I felt less immersed

This time, how well do you think you memorised the actions that took place in front of you?

- I remembered everything
- I remembered the majority of the actions
- I remembered most of the actions
- I only remembered some of the actions
- I remembered nothing at all

Did you find it more or less difficult to follow the sequence of events between the two parts than when you watched video 1?

- Following the events was easier
- My experience was unchanged
- Following the events was more difficult

(If easier) Why do you think it was easier/more difficult?

On a scale of 1 to 5, rate the difficulty of following the sequence of events between the two rooms.

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- 1= Very difficult/5= Very easy

Can you briefly describe the scenario (story) you observed?

Can you briefly describe the events (actions) you observed?

Can you briefly describe the characters (names, characteristics, etc.)? For you, what were the most important or memorable moments in the story?

Why?

Is there anything else you would like to share about your experience?

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11. OUTLOOK

The continuation of this study necessitates dual trajectories: the extension of the experimental environments and the refinement of analytical methodologies.

In addressing the former outlined in deliverable 5.3.2, we intend to conduct extended cognitive tests with all the environments currently available in the industry: new generation VR headsets, 270° devices and the 360°/180° dome. We will also work with content created specifically for these environments.

Augmenting our experimental framework, we will avail ourselves of a shared research unit at the UCA COCOLAB laboratory with state-of-the-art eye-tracking instrumentation and expert personnel proficient in these investigative techniques.

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Disclaimer

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